

Implementing Reproducible Cookbook Environments for Advanced Analyses on Science Gateways

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Abstract—Science gateways face challenges supporting new users that require complex environments for High-Performance Computing (HPC). To address barriers to entry caused by complex environments, an application was developed to integrate science gateways with reproducible environments, reducing barriers to entry. Leveraging concepts from systems like Binder and Google Colab, we created reproducible computational cookbooks — a flexible framework that supports containerizing and sharing environments and workflows across users for advanced computing resources. These cookbooks utilize standardized repositories and Docker images, which simplifies the environment setup providing access through science gateways. By employing a developers’ gateway, users can register and share applications to enhance collaboration. Once registered, applications facilitate collaboration in HPC research, ensures consistency across environmental dependencies, and enables access to reusable analytical workflows. This paper outlines the cookbook system’s development, demonstrating its potential to broaden access and impact in HPC research environments.

Index Terms—High-Performance Computing, Reproducibility, Science Gateways, Complex Environments, Workflow

I. INTRODUCTION

Complex research questions often require difficult to install environments that can create barriers to entry for new HPC users. The Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), a leading academic HPC institution, currently has limited options to

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support users with low maintenance and reproducible environments. For many technically inclined users, this limited support is enough. Many research projects can build upon a foundation of previous HPC research projects. However, the amount of data available is ever increasing, and more users are needing access to higher performance computers. These users may not be comfortable with the command line interface or other technical aspects of currents. Science Gateways have been an answer to these technical problems. Science gateways provide a web based user interfaces without command line interactions, thus reducing barriers to entry [1], [2]. To date, TACC has lacked an effective workflow to connect the science gateway front end with standardized and reproducible environments. This paper discusses the workflow and application developed to provide this capability.

Various systems have been developed to improve scientific reproducibility by reducing required installation times and the variability within complex environments on scientific computing [3]. Systems such as Binder [3], Google Colab [4], and Open OnDemand [5] which provide a platform for creating the provided environments and running code, enabling users without extensive programming skills to rapidly interact with and utilize the tools without standing up and manage the underlying environment themselves. Other projects have focused on organizing training and environments specific to their field, for example Project Pythia for the geosciences [6], or using Google Colab for training economic students [7]. Data analysis workflows often use similar packages and the devel-

opment of reproducible computational cookbooks provides the means to separate out the complex environment setup from the downstream data research work and enables the sharing of computational environments between collaborators and across projects. This improves reproducibility and transparency of research project. While effective, using cloud systems such as Google Colab or Binder at scale can be quite costly, especially if significant computational resources are needed. Many HPC systems leverage the Open OnDemand infrastructure, which allows the user to develop and share applications. However, TACC currently uses the TAPIS infrastructure an alternative system that provides a user-friendly and modern Web UI that best allows TACC’s users to utilize our HPC systems without needing to use the command line. TACC’s support for Academic research can significantly reduce the cost and make the work financially viable for users with access.

TACC users have access to powerful systems, such as Lonestar 6, but a number of constraints have limited user access to these resources. First, installing software includes navigating TACC security requirements which creates an extra layer of difficulty. Second, the compute nodes are hidden behind a login node which requires a customized JupyterLab [8] setup to run as an interactive web session [8]. A typical Jupyter install is feasible [9], however varying scientific domains require different components of the Jupyter environment, and as the environments become increasingly complex, reproducibility across users becomes more difficult. This is where the Binder project comes into play, the binder design provides a standard format to containerize repositories.

II. CURRENT STATUS OF TACC SCIENCE GATEWAYS

The cookbook system is designed to support complex environments (Fig. 1). Historically, TACC has received fewer requests for certain packages, such as new software or geospatial libraries (ex. GDAL, OSGEO), but as this field has expanded further into the High Performance Computing space, users require more support for these packages and TACC has encountered issues providing these resources. Typically, when a package has a low request rate on the system, users are directed to install the package to their \$WORK [10] space on the machines. However, when investigating how users might install these packages for themselves, we discovered that a complex process was involved in almost every installation. For environments such as GDAL, pip or conda install commands were insufficient because they rely on the presence of libraries the systems lack by default. Direct installation proves difficult as these packages’ default to installing to the root space, a restricted space for TACC users. Most users seeking these packages were not Linux software specialists who were familiar with how to work around such barriers.

With these complex software, we initially settled on system installation by the administrators, but this approach required significant maintenance due to the number of dependencies a package (e.g. GDAL or NLP). As such, this solution requires frequent updates to all the associated software and libraries, and still, users need to modify their environments to ensure

these packages are properly loaded in their \$PATH before submitting their jobs. All of these issues require a level of HPC computing skill that creates a significant barrier to entry for newer users.

III. USE CASE: COOKBOOK SOLUTION

The initial use case for this project was the development of a cookbook environment that supports Natural Language Processing (NLP). NLP research provides a perfect test case for standing up this service on advanced computing resources. NLP requires complex computing installation and frequently involves researchers from non-technical backgrounds. These non-technical users lack the requisite programming skills to independently set up and maintain the necessary compute environments. Additionally, many projects of interest involve the analysis of potentially sensitive materials (example: unredacted interview data, critical infrastructure details) where maintaining control of the raw data, interim analytical data outputs, and resultant data products is critical.

The initial use case was implemented codesigning a solution with researchers on a Navigating the New Arctic research project (NNA Team). The NNA team uses mixed method approaches for evaluating the gaps between the socio-cultural understanding of water resources in remote, rural Alaska and the technical knowledge about the operational engineering specifications of the water system infrastructure that serves isolated communities. Using the cookbook service, TACC installed foundational large language models on HPC resources and setup a complex cookbook service to support multi-method NLP analyses that support the use of traditional NLP libraries, such as BERTopic, and emerging workflows that incorporate LLMs in a private environment. The social scientists and environmental systems engineers tested the cookbook systems using corpora from 1) interview data collections with rural Alaskan community members and 2) technical water infrastructure systems training materials. The NLP cookbook provides access to a new group of HPC users and helps complete advanced analysis was compared with manually coded results social scientists, and lead to the creation of a module in a software application called Sites and Stories. This module is in development and will provide AI-enabled support for modeling with stakeholders [11].

The cookbook services leverage science gateways and TAPIS to provide users complex environments for interactive scientific experiments. TAPIS is an API that connects to TACC allowing users to organize and submit jobs to HPC systems [12]. We adapted features from the Binder container standards to make the environments easy to develop from templates. While the cookbooks workflow can be used for a variety of environments, we focused on creating a flexible JupyterLab cookbook that can generate reproducible environments.

A. Required Repositories

The TACC cookbooks require two repositories to create a working application. The first repository [13] provides the Anaconda environment and the pip environment files in a

Fig. 1. Workflow and architecture for the TACC cookbook application. Users can 1) fork a template from github to create the appropriate repositories; 2) register and share the application with the science gateway.

format (stored in a “.binder” folder at the top of the repository) to work with Binder. Using this standard enables both files to be used for the anaconda environment. Note: the anaconda file is the primary environment file, while the pip file is only for dependencies that either (a) require large amounts of space or (b) are only available via pip. We separate the two environmental files to reduce the size of the cache required when creating the environment, as Pip allows for a no-cache install while Anaconda does not. This repository is pulled when creating the docker image for the container.

The second repository contains a Docker image forked from the TACC Jupyter Lab application notebooks [14]. The docker image sets up a JupyterLab environment, and then downloads the first repository to install the required dependencies. The application can further be configured to load and run additional software. By separating these two repositories, we can provide standardized repositories that require minimal customization for differing environments. This docker image has GitHub actions included in the repository to generate the docker image automatically.

Both repositories have been generated as templates living within GitHub.com. The current templates create a hello world JupyterLab the users can create on TACC systems. In the case of the NLP environment, we added a few functions that ensure the Ollama software [15] is installed and running as a service on the compute node. Ollama is a software that enables efficient loading and use of LLM models for Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG [16]) of information within a corpora. Ollama provides an API that is queried through prompts, and is initiated through bash scripts. The NLP cookbook repositories provide examples of the working use case [17], [18].

B. Registering an Application

For development and production purposes, cookbooks need to be registered within the TACC systems. Previously, users would need to use TAPIS with either their own calls or using the Python API to register their application. For this project we developed a developers gateway [19] that allows users to register their application using a UI.

This gateway requires the user to register their app.json file with the gateway (Fig 2). The app.json file follows the TAPIS example and provides the list of choices a user can choose when submitting their application. This includes the queues that the application should use, and any other variables the image will need to run. For example, the NLP cookbook leverages GPUs for analysis, therefore the queues without GPUs have been removed from the drop down. Examples of these files can be found in the docker template repository [14].

Once the application has been registered the user can decide who to share the application with, whether this is a science gateway (ex. PTDataX [20]) or a specific allocation. By allowing the user to share to a specific allocation, we enable users to share environments in a collaborative manner, without publishing their application for all of TACC to access.

C. Availability on the Science Gateways

Once an application has been registered and shared it can become available on a science gateway. If the user is sharing with collaborators, the application will show up in the My Apps tab, however if the user wants to share it with the entire science gateway, they will need to request an admin add it to the cookbooks tab. Once the TAPIS cookbook application is running on a science gateway portal, the containerized cookbook allows the application to run across any execution system.

IV. CONCLUSION

Supporting users with complex software needs is a difficult problem, and a lack of this support at TACC has proved a significant research impediment for TACC users. In this paper we outline the process we have developed to reduce barriers to entry through cookbooks thereby increasing access and impact. The TACC reproducible computational cookbook services show promise for streamlining the reuse and sharing of workflows and providing users a variety of complex services on HPC systems without the need for root access. This workflow can be used both by science gateway managers, and also individual users to improve reproducibility and collaboration.

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